

An Epidemiological Study and Trends of Rhinosporidiosis over a Period of Twelve Years in a Tertiary Hospital in Burdwan, West Bengal**Nikhilesh Dewasi¹, Ankita Chakraborty², Soumik Dandapat³, Surupa Chowdhury⁴, Rupam Karmakar⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital²Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Prafulla Chandra Sen Govt Medical College & Hospital, Arambagh³Junior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital⁵Professor and Head, Department of Pathology, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital

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Abstract:**Background:** Rhinosporidiosis is a chronic granulomatous disease due to *Rhinosporidium seeberi* that affects mainly nasal and nasopharyngeal mucosa. The condition is endemic in some regions of India, such as West Bengal. Longitudinal data from this region are still limited.

This research was conducted to describe the clinico-pathological and epidemiological profile of histopathologically proven rhinosporidiosis cases and analyze yearly trends over a 12-year period in a tertiary care facility in eastern India.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective record-based study was done at the Department of Pathology, Burdwan Medical College and Hospital. All histologically diagnosed cases of rhinosporidiosis from January 2013 to August 2024 were taken into consideration. Pertinent data like age, sex, domicile, clinical features, site of lesion, and histopathological findings were obtained from departmental records and analyzed using SPSS software (version 23.0, IBM Corp). Trends of cases per year were plotted. Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) and Periodic acid Schiff (PAS) stain were used over all histological slides.**Results:** 104 histologically diagnosed cases of rhinosporidiosis were analyzed over a period of 12 years. The patients were predominantly male (72.11%) and almost half of them were ≤ 20 years of age (47.12%), followed by 21–40 years (30.77%). Chi-square test demonstrated considerable variation between age and gender distribution ($p < 0.001$). Lesions were most commonly seen in patient's ≤ 40 years (77.88%). The most frequent site of involvement was the nose in both genders and age groups, though there was no significant variation by age or gender in the site of lesions. Rural origins predominated (74.04%), and 91.35% had a history of pond bathing, both of which were significantly linked to rhinosporidiosis ($p < 0.001$). Leukocytosis was not seen in the majority (91.35%), but eosinophilia was found in 38.46%, which varied from mild to severe, both of which were significantly associated ($p < 0.001$). Blood group was not related to the disease. Sessile lesions (58.65%) morphologically were the most common, but variations from pedunculated forms were not statistically significant. Polypoidal masses, epistaxis, and rhinorrhea were common symptoms. Ocular mass and watering of the eye were the presentation of ocular lesions. Trend analysis revealed that there was an overall decreasing incidence with a marked decline in 2022 and a rebound in 2023.**Conclusions:** Rhinosporidiosis, a chronic disease linked to pond bathing, mainly affects rural young males. Public health awareness may reduce incidence and aid future eradication efforts.**Keywords:** Epidemiological Trend, Granulomatous Infection, Histopathology, Nasal Polyp, Rhinosporidiosis, *Rhinosporidium seeberi*.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Rhinosporidiosis is a rare and interesting infection first described in 1900 by Guillermo Seeber in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Initially, he had proposed that it was caused by a fungus, which was subsequently proved when Ashworth cultured the causative agent in 1923. Ashworth also

characterized its life cycle and gave it the name *Rhinosporidium seeberi*. [1] Because of the absence of available culture techniques and animal models, its taxonomy has remained controversial. Initially, it was placed under sporozoans and subsequently under fungus, but molecular research

has prompted its reclassification under a unique clade of aquatic protistan parasites called Ichthyosporidia (Mesomycetozoa).[2] It is a chronic granulomatous infectious disease presenting with hyperplastic, friable, reddish polypoid growths, which are either pedunculated or sessile.

Rhinosporidiosis is mainly seen in mucosal and subcutaneous tissues.[3] Infection is caused by transepithelial inoculation when sporangiospores penetrate traumatized epithelium.[4] Contact with infected water sources like ponds or lakes, or infected soil, provides an entry point for spores to penetrate the nasal mucosa. They develop into sporangia in the submucosal layer once inside, which later rupture to discharge endospores into the tissue. This is due to the production of typical soft, friable, polypoidal "strawberry-like" masses bearing white spots as mature sporangia.[1,5]

The nasopharynx and nose are the most frequent locations, with extra-nasal disease occurring infrequently. In a minority of patients, the process can spread to the oropharynx, larynx, trachea, conjunctiva, and lacrimal sac, as well as to other sites such as lips, palate, buccal mucosa, genital mucosa, skin, scalp, and bone. Disseminated infections are uncommon, and spontaneous resolution of nasal polypoidal lesions has only been occasionally reported.[4]

A careful history, especially about bathing and occupational history of exposure to stagnant water, is important in clinical diagnosis. Final proof is obtained from histopathological examination of resected tissue samples.[6-9]

The disease is endemic in the tropics, highly prevalent in South and Central India, Sri Lanka, and Argentina.[10] It has been described in about 70 countries, including those in Europe, North and South America; especially Brazil, Argentina, and Mexico; with sporadic cases from Colombia, Venezuela, Uganda, Madagascar, Ghana, Iran, Russia, and Southeast Asia.[6] In Western nations, cases are mostly seen in immigrants who probably contracted the disease in endemic areas.[11]

Rhinosporidiosis is found to be prevalent all over India and is considered endemic in certain states like Tamil Nadu, Chhattisgarh, Kerala, and Orissa. India and Sri Lanka are responsible for nearly 90% of cases reported worldwide, suggesting that the disease is much more prevalent in India than elsewhere in the world.[12,13]

Studies have revealed that the disease, rhinosporidiosis, is common in the southwestern area of West Bengal, India, with a significantly high incidence identified in Bankura and Purulia districts and the surrounding regions of Birbhum, Paschim Medinipur, and Burdwan. The results point towards the endemic significance of the

disease in this region of the state.[14,15] While a fall in reported cases has been noted in recent years, it is still important to determine if there have been any alterations in the characteristics of the disease, such as its site of infection, clinical presentation, and histopathological features.

Burdwan Medical College, which is in Purba Bardhaman district, is a large referral tertiary care center for a largely rural population. With its patient flow, the institution offers a valuable chance to examine trends in rhinosporidiosis cases over time. This research intends to assess the annual trends, clinical presentation, and histological diagnosis of rhinosporidiosis cases within the region. Through this, it hopes to establish whether there have been changes in the epidemiology or presentation of the disease, which would have implications for diagnosis, treatment, and public health interventions.

Materials and Methods

This was an observational, retrospective, record-based study undertaken in the Department of Pathology of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital during June 2024 to September 2024. Institutional records were accessed for data on all histopathologically proven cases of rhinosporidiosis from specimens received by the pathology department during the last twelve years (January 2013 to August 2024). The research involved 104 cases with both clinical and histopathological evidence, along with complete patient history regarding personal habits, living area, bathing habits, occupational history, pre-anesthetic checkup, blood reports, and ABO blood group. Patients with nasal masses caused by diseases other than rhinosporidiosis or patients with incomplete records were not included.

Leukocytosis denotes a rise in the white blood cell (WBC) count. Typically, a WBC count surpassing 11,000 cells/ μ L is deemed leukocytosis.¹⁶ Eosinophilia is defined as an increase of circulating eosinophils >5% of the circulating leukocyte. Based on the counts, eosinophilia was subdivided into three categories: mild (6-10%), moderate (11-20%), and severe (>21%).¹⁷

Histopathological specimens were stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) and Periodic Acid-Schiff (PAS) staining. The diagnosis of rhinosporidial infection relied on the identification of thick-walled sporangia full of many endospores in a fibrovascular stroma with chronic inflammatory cell infiltration, according to expert advice.¹⁸

Ethical approval of the study was received from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Burdwan Medical College and Hospital. The data were verified for completeness and consistency prior to

analysis by using SPSS software (version 23.0, IBM Corp). The data were described in tables by frequency and percentages, whereas categorical variables were analyzed by using the Chi-square test with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Total 104 histologically proven rhinosporidiosis cases had been taken over a period of 12 years. **Table 1** shows the distribution of study participants

($n=104$) by age and gender. Most participants were male (72.11%). Almost half of the participants were in the ≤ 20 years category (47.12%), followed by the 21–40 years category (30.77%), with very few participants aged >60 years (3.84%). The results of chi-square analysis indicated significant deviation from equal proportion for both gender ($\chi^2=20.35$, $p < 0.001$) and age distribution ($\chi^2=42.23$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 1: Distribution of study subjects according to age and gender (n=104).

Gender	Age (Years) (%)				Total (%)
	≤ 20	21-40	41-60	>60	
Male	37 (35.58)	28 (26.92)	8 (7.69)	2 (1.92)	75 (72.11)
Female	12 (11.54)	4 (3.85)	11 (10.58)	2 (1.92)	29 (27.89)
Total	49 (47.12)	32 (30.77)	19 (18.27)	4 (3.84)	104 (100.00)

Table 2 shows the distribution of study subjects by the site of the lesion, stratified for gender and age. The majority of the lesions (81/104, 77.88%) were seen in subjects of ≤ 40 years of age. In subject's ≤ 40 years of age, nasal involvement (49.38%) was highest, followed by nasopharyngeal (25.93%), and ocular (16.05%). In subjects >40 years of age, nasal lesions were highest (69.56%), followed by nasopharyngeal (13.04%) and ocular involvement (8.70%). But this difference in proportion between

site of the lesion among different age groups was not statistically significant ($\chi^2=3.32$, $p=0.352$). Similarly, in males ($n=75$), nasal involvement (53.33%) was the highest, followed by nasopharyngeal (21.33%), and ocular (14.67%). In women ($n=29$), nasal lesions (55.17%) was again the highest, closely followed by nasopharyngeal (27.59%) and ocular involvement (13.79%). There was no statistically significant relationship between gender and site of lesion ($\chi^2=1.64$, $p=0.652$).

Table 2: Distribution of study subjects according to the site of lesion with age and gender (n=104).

Demographic Characteristics		Site of lesion [Frequency(percentage)]					Test Statistic
		Total	Nose	Nasopharynx	Eye	Other site [#]	
Age (years)	≤ 40	81 (100.00)	40 (49.38)	21 (25.93)	13 (16.05)	7 (8.64)	$X^2=3.32$, df=3, P=0.35*
	>40	23 (100.00)	16 (69.56)	3 (13.04)	2 (8.70)	2 (8.70)	
Gender	Male	75 (100.00)	40 (53.33)	16 (21.33)	11 (14.67)	8 (10.67)	$X^2=1.64$, df=3, P=0.65*
	Female	29 (100.00)	16 (55.17)	8 (27.59)	4 (13.79)	1 (3.45)	
Total		104 (100.00)	56 (53.85)	24 (23.08)	15 (14.42)	9 (8.65)	

[#]Other site includes mass in parotid duct, cheek, sinonasal area, and disseminated lesion. *Fisher exact test.

Table 3 shows the socio-clinical characteristics of the study participants. Majority of the participants were from rural area (74.04%). There was a statistically significant association between residence and occurrence of lesion ($\chi^2=24.04$, $p < 0.001$). History of bathing in ponds was reported by 91.35% of the participants, and this was also found to be statistically significant ($\chi^2=71.12$, $p < 0.001$). In relation to hematological characteristics, leukocytosis was absent in 91.35% of the subjects, with a statistically significant association ($\chi^2=71.12$, $p < 0.001$). Eosinophilia was

present in 38.46% of the subjects, which was classified as mild (22.11%), moderate (10.58%), and severe (5.77%), and was significantly associated ($\chi^2=79.92$, $p < 0.001$). Blood group of the participants was not statistically significantly associated with the presence of lesions ($\chi^2=2.54$, $p=0.468$). In gross morphology, the lesions were found to be predominantly sessile (58.65%), though the difference in prevalence between sessile and pedunculated forms were not statistically significant ($\chi^2=3.12$, $p=0.078$).

Table 3: Distribution of study subjects according to socio-clinical characteristics (n=104).

Socio-clinical characteristics (n=104)		Frequency	Percentage	Test Statistic*
Residence	Rural	77	74.04	X ² =24.04, df=1, P <0.001
	Urban	27	25.96	
Pond bathing history	Present	95	91.35	X ² =71.12, df=1, P<0.001
	Absent	9	8.65	
Blood group	A	27	25.96	X ² =2.54, df=3, P= 0.468
	B	24	23.08	
	AB	21	20.19	
	O	32	30.77	
Leukocytosis	Present	9	8.65	X ² =71.12, df=1, P <0.001
	Absent	95	91.35	
Eosinophilia	Absent	64	61.54	X ² =79.92, df=3, P<0.001.
	Mild	23	22.11	
	Moderate	11	10.58	
	Severe	6	5.77	
Gross characteristics	Sessile	61	58.65	X ² =3.12, df=1, P=0.078
	Pedunculated	43	41.35	

*Chi-square test for Goodness of Fit

Figure 1 shows distribution of study participants according to their presenting symptoms. For nasal, nasopharyngeal, or sinonasal masses, polypoidal lesions were the most frequent, followed by epistaxis, rhinorrhea, and nasal obstruction. In ocular lesions, polypoidal masses and watering of eyes were most frequent.

Figure 1: Bar diagram showing distribution of study participants according to their presenting symptoms. *Multiple response taken.

Trends of rhinosporidiosis in last twelve years showed that incidence of rhinosporidiosis is gradually decreasing [Figure 2]. But we had seen

that there was sudden decrease in incidence in the year of 2022 followed by rising of incidence in the year of 2023.

Figure 2: Line diagram showing year wise trend of rhinosporidiosis cases.

Discussion

Rhinosporidiosis is a chronic granulomatous infective disorder producing polypoidal, pedunculated, soft tissue mass.[17] Aim of this present study was to document the clinico-pathological, epidemiological presentation and year wise trend of rhinosporidiosis cases in a Tertiary Care Center in West Bengal. Retrospective analysis was done using secondary data of 104 histopathologically confirmed cases after fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The predominance of males, as seen in this study (72.11%), agrees with the findings of many previous studies. A hospital-based epidemiological study in Purulia, India,[19] also gave a male-to-female ratio of about 1.44:1 and assigned the higher frequency among males to increased exposure to contaminated water on account of outdoor activities and occupation. Studies done in Raipur [20] and Kolkata [21] also gave evidence of male preponderance, the male-to-female ratios being between 1.3:1 to 3:1. The increased prevalence among males is frequently attributed to behavioral reasons like greater probability of bathing in stagnant water, fishing, and agriculture, which expose the individual to an increased risk of contact with *Rhinosporidium seeberi* [8]. Some authors also opined that the effect of estrogen in females may provide some protection from inflammatory diseases such as rhinosporidiosis.[22]

Regarding the age distribution, almost half of the subjects of the current study were ≤ 20 years old (47.12%), followed by the 21–40 years group (30.77%), whereas only 3.84% were >60 years old. Chandran M, et al.[11] also found, in their study, that rhinosporidiosis was seen most commonly among the 10–20 year age group. But considerable deviations in the majority age groups most affected have been noted in varying studies, depending on geographical as well as cultural factors. A survey in

Sri Lanka [8] showed the highest rate among people aged 10-29 years. Penagos et al.[2] validated in a meta-analysis that the younger age groups are more at risk due to increased contact with environmental reservoirs during recreational and household activities. The substantial departure from an equal ratio for both gender ($\chi^2=20.35$, $p<0.001$) and age distribution ($\chi^2=42.23$, $p<0.001$) in the current study indicates these underlying demographic and behavioral factors.

Regarding the location of the lesion, nose was the most prevalent site in younger (49.38%) as well as elderly (69.56%) volunteers, followed by nasopharyngeal and ocular involvement. These are in agreement with earlier reports in which nasal mucosa was also found to be the most involved site because it comes into direct contact with polluted water while bathing and engaging in other activities [23]. A southern Indian study presented that 65% of all occurrences were nasal lesions, followed by nasopharyngeal (20%) and ocular (10%) involvement [24]. Nasal involvement is more prevalent due to the pathogen's natural point of entry by way of nasal mucosa, with trauma or abrasions allowing for spore penetration [8]. The variations of lesion distribution with age and gender did not prove to be statistically significant, suggesting that the site of lesions could be more dependent on environmental exposure than demographic circumstances.

This study also pointed towards significant socio-clinical trends. The majority of the subjects (74.04%) belonged to rural backgrounds, exemplifying the endemic nature of rhinosporidiosis in areas with poor sanitation and excessive reliance on open water sources. A strong association was observed between rural residence and the occurrence of lesions ($\chi^2=24.04$, $p<0.001$), in line with the results from analogous studies in rural Sri Lanka [8]. Pond bathing history was noted by 91.35% of the participants, demonstrating a very

strong association with the development of rhinosporidiosis ($\chi^2=71.12$, $p<0.001$). Various studies have made similar observations, emphasizing that stagnant water bodies are the most important reservoirs for *R. seeberi* [7,23]. In a West Bengal study,[21] 82% of patients had at least a history of bathing in ponds or rivers before the onset of the disease.

As for hematological findings, the majority of participants (91.35%) did not exhibit leukocytosis, this was statistically significant ($\chi^2=71.12$, $p<0.001$). Eosinophilia was also seen in 38.46% of subjects, with substantial variation between mild (22.11%), moderate (10.58%), and severe (5.77%) forms ($\chi^2=79.92$, $p<0.001$). These hematological findings are similar to previous reports [25–28]. This is expected from the immune response pattern to parasitic infection, where eosinophilia is the rule owing to the chronic inflammatory nature of rhinosporidiosis [29]. Raised eosinophils indicate a type I hypersensitivity reaction to the sporangia and endospores of *R. seeberi* [30].

Distribution of blood groups was also not related to lesion development, as has been confirmed in other research that found no correlation of blood group with susceptibility to rhinosporidiosis [1,19]. Gross morphology was also characterized by a majority

of sessile lesions (58.65%), and the difference between sessile and pedunculated types was not statistically different.

Symptom-wise, polypoidal lesions constituted the most common presentation in the nasal as well as the ocular forms and reflect the traditional clinical presentation of rhinosporidiosis. Epistaxis, rhinorrhea, and nasal blockade were other predominant findings, compatible with the mucosal manifestation found in earlier studies [1,8,17,31].

In our study, histopathological examination was done by using Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) and Periodic acid Schiff (PAS) staining [Figure 3a & 3b]. Histopathological study done over biopsied or resected specimens can identify various stages of pathogen helping to confirm final diagnosis [26]. Histological section shows multiple thick walled sporangium in various stages of maturation with intense acute and chronic mixed inflammatory cell infiltration. Overlying mucosa may show hyperplasia with squamous metaplasia. Giant cell reaction may occur due to rupture of sporangia [18,26]. Outer wall of sporangia and endospores can be better visualized by using stains like PAS, Mucicarmine, Gomori's methenamine-silver stain etc [18,26,32].

Figure 3a: H&E stained section from nasal rhinosporidiosis shows presence of multiple spherules and intense inflammatory reaction with associated squamous metaplasia (H&E stain, 40x). Figure 3b: PAS stained section from nasal rhinosporidiosis shows multiple periodic acid-schiff positive, refractile, magenta coloured spores within capsule (PAS stain, 40x).

Histopathological examination is gold standard for diagnosis of rhinosporidiosis. But in rare instance diagnosis may be missed. Commonest cause of diagnostic error is faulty selection of the portion of the polypoidal mass for study, containing no or only few rhinosporidial tissue, where as other

portions show typical picture[17]. Other rare causes of false negative histopathological diagnosis include absence of well-developed outer covering of sporangium, presence of only fragments of sporangium without endospores or absence of

typical rhinosporidial bodies as a consequence of possible immunological reactions [8].

The 12-year trend analysis indicated a gradual fall in rhinosporidiosis incidence with an abrupt drop in 2022 and then a resurgence in 2023. This trend can be an indicator of better public health practices, enhanced awareness, and diminished contact with infected water sources. Cyclical patterns have also been described in endemic areas where the dynamics of transmission are determined by seasonal rainfall, water quality, and patterns of human activity [8]. There is a sudden fall of number of patients in the year of 2022, may be due to COVID-19 causing complete lockdown and decrease the number of elective operation in government hospital.

Conclusions

Rhinosporidiosis is a chronic granulomatous disorder. Pond-bathing is a major risk factor for this disease. Male gender, young adults, agricultural occupations, rural populations are mostly affected. Patients most commonly present with polypoidal lesion in of nose and nasopharynx. Histopathology is gold standard for diagnosis of rhinosporidiosis. Special stains are recommended for difficult cases. This study also shows that public health awareness may help to reduce the incidence of this disease and eventually eradication of this disease may be possible in future.

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